

Study on Fixed Point Result for Special Mappings

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Abstract: In this paper, study on existence of fixed point result for mappings defined on CCM (Complete Cone Metric)-Spaces (X, ρ) satisfying a G-Contractive condition depended on another function.

Key words: Contractive condition, fixed point, sequentially convergent, sub sequentially convergent.

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1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Banach contraction principle is the first and foremost important result in fixed point theory it was appeared in Banach's [6] thesis in 1922. The Banach contraction principle in 1968 Kannan [12] analyzed a substantially new type of contraction condition. Later on many authors were inspired with these results, extended and generalized in different ways (see for e.g. [1-5, 7-11, 13-21]). Huang and Zhang [9] introduced the cone metric space, where the set of real numbers is replaced by an ordered Banach space. They obtained some fixed point results in cone metric space. Later on many authors were inspired by these results; they have been extending these results in different dimensions (see for e.g. [1-8, 8-11,13-22]). In recent developments in this area for non explosive map in cone metric spaces (see for e.g. [1-6]. Recently Beiravand, Moradi, et. al. [7] obtained two fixed point theorems for special mappings. In this paper we proved a fixed point result for special mappings.

The following are need in our main results which are due to [7,9].

Definition 1.1. Let B_1 be a real Banach space and Q is a subset of B_1 , Q_1 is called a cone iff

- (i). Q_1 is closed, non empty and $Q_1 \neq 0$,
- (ii). $\alpha_1 x + \beta_1 y \in Q_1$ for all $x, y \in Q_1$ and α_1, β_1 are non negative numbers,
- (iii). $Q_1 \cap (-Q_1) = 0$.

Definition 1.2. Given a cone $Q_1 \subset B_1$, we define a partial ordering \leq with respect to Q_1 by : $x_1 \leq y_1$ iff $y_1 - x_1 \in Q_1$. We shall write $x_1 < y_1$ to indicate that $x_1 \leq y_1$ but $x_1 \neq y_1$, while $x_1 \ll y_1$ will stand for $y_1 - x_1 \in$ interior of Q_1 .

Definition 1.3. TThe cone Q_1 is called normal if there is a number $L_1 > 0$ such that for all $x_1, y_1 \in B_1$, $0 \leq x_1 \leq y_1$ implies $\|x_1\| \leq L_1 \|y_1\|$, where $\|\cdot\|$ is the norm in B_1 . In this case the number L_1 is called the normal constant of Q_1 .

Definition 1.4. Let X_1 be a non- empty set. Suppose the $\rho : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ satisfies the following: (a). $\rho(x_1, y_1) > 0$ for all $x_1, y_1 \in X_1$ and $\rho(x_1, y_1) = 0$ if and only if $x_1 = y_1$.

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(b). $\rho(x_1, y_1) = \rho(y_1, x_1)$, for all $x_1, y_1 \in X_1$.

(c). $\rho(x_1, y_1) \leq \rho(x_1, z_1) + \rho(z_1, y_1)$, for all $x_1, y_1 \in X_1$. Then ρ is called a cone metric on X_1 , and (X_1, ρ) is called a cone metric space.

Definition 1.5. Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM(Cone Metric) space. Let (x_{1n}) be a sequence in X_1 and $x_1 \in X$. If for every $c_1 \in B_1$, $c \gg 0$ there is N_1 such that for all $n_1 > N_1$, $\rho(x_{1n_1}, x_1) \ll c$, then (x_{1n_1}) is said to be convergent to x_1 and x_1 is the limit of (x_{1n}) . We denote this $x_{1n} \rightarrow x_1$ as $n_1 \rightarrow \infty$.

Definition 1.6. Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM(Cone Metric) space. Let (x_{1n}) be a sequence in X_1 and $x_1 \in X_1$. If for every $c \in B_1$, $c \gg 0$ there is N_1 such that for all $n_1, m_1 > N_1$, $\rho(x_{1n_1}, x_{1m_1}) \ll c$, then (x_{1n}) is said to be Cauchy sequence in X_1 .

Definition 1.7. Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM(Cone Metric) space. If every Cauchy sequence is convergent, then X_1 is called a CCM(Complete Cone Metric)-space.

We introduce the A_1 -Contraction and A_1 -Contractive functions and then we extend theorem 2.6 of [7] metric space to cone metric space.

Definition 1.8. Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM (Cone Metric)- space and $A_1, B_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ be two functions. A mapping B_1 is said to be a A_1 -contraction if there exists $\alpha_1 \in (0, 1]$ such that for

$$\rho(A_1 B_1 x_1, B_1 A_1 y_1) \leq \lambda_1 \rho(A_1 x_1, A_1 y_1) \text{ for all } x_1, y_1 \in X_1. \quad (1)$$

Definition 1.9. . Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM (Cone Metric)- space. A mapping $A_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ is said to be sequentially convergent if we have, for every sequence x_{1n} , if $\{A_1 x_{1n}\}$ is convergence then $\{x_{1n}\}$ is also convergence.

Definition 1.10. . Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM (Cone Metric)- space. A mapping $A_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ is said to be sub sequentially convergent if we have, for every sequence x_{1n} , if $\{A_1 x_{1n}\}$ is convergence then $\{x_{1n}\}$ is also convergence subsequence.

Proposition 1.1. Let (X_1, ρ) be a CM (Cone Metric)- space, then every function $A_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ is sub sequentially convergent and every continuous function $A_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ is sub sequentially convergent.

2. Main Result

Theorem 2.1. Let (X_1, ρ) be CCM (Complete Cone Metric) -space and P_1 be a normal cone with normal constant L_1 and $A_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$ be one -to- one continuous and sub sequentially convergent mapping. Then every A_1 -contraction (1) continuous function $B_1 : X_1 \rightarrow X_1$, B_1 has a unique fixed point. Also if A_1 sequentially convergent then each x_{10} in X_1 the sequence of iterations $\{B_1^{n_1} x_{10}\}$ converges to this fixed point.

Proof. For every x_1, x_2 in X_1

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(A_1 x_1, A_1 x_2) &\leq \rho(A_1 x_1, A_1 B_1 x_1) + \rho(A_1 B_1 x_1, A_1 B_1 x_2) + \rho(A_1 B_1 x_2, A_1 x_2), \\ &\leq \rho(A_1 x_1, A_1 B_1 x_1) + \lambda_1 \rho(A_1 x_1, A_1 x_2) + \rho(A_1 B_1 x_2, A_1 x_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\rho(A_1x_1, A_1x_2) \leq \frac{1}{1-\lambda_1} [\rho(A_1x_1, A_1x_2) + \rho(A_1B_1x_2, A_1x_2)]. \quad (2)$$

Now $x_0 \in X_1$ and define iterative sequence, $\{x_n\}$ by $x_{n+1} = B_1x_n$ (equally $x_n = B_1^n x_0$), $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$.
By (1) for any indices $m, n \in N_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(A_1x_n, A_1B_1x_m) &= \rho(A_1B_1^n x_0, A_1B_1^m x_0), \\ &\leq \frac{1}{1-\lambda_1} [\rho(A_1B_1^n x_0, A_1B_1^{n+1} x_0) + \rho(A_1B_1^{m+1} x_0, A_1B_1^m x_0)], \\ \rho(A_1B_1^n x_0, A_1B_1^m x_0) &\leq \frac{\lambda^n + \lambda^m}{1-\lambda_1} \rho(A_1x_0, A_1B_1x_0). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

By the normality

$$\|\rho(A_1B_1^n x_0, A_1B_1^m x_0)\| \leq \frac{\lambda^n + \lambda^m}{1-\lambda_1} L_1 \|\rho(A_1x_0, A_1B_1x_0)\|.$$

Where L_1 is a normal constant. Letting $n, m \rightarrow \infty$, we get that

$$\|\rho(A_1B_1^n x_0, A_1B_1^m x_0)\| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n, m \rightarrow \infty.$$

Therefore, $\{A_1B_1^n x_0\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Since

$$X_1 \text{ is complete there exists } u_1 \in X_1 \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_1B_1^n x_0 = u_1. \quad (4)$$

Since A_1 is sub sequentially convergent, $\{B_1^n x_0\}$ has a convergent subsequence. So there exists $v_1 \in X_1$ such that $\{n_r\}, r = 1, 2, \dots$ such that $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} B_1^{n_r} x_0 = v_1$.

Hence, $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} A_1B_1^{n_r} x_0 = A_1v_1$.

$$\text{And by (3) we conclude that } A_1v_1 = u_1. \quad (5)$$

Since B_1 is continuous and $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} B_1^{n_r} x_0 = v_1$, then $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} B_1^{n_r+1} x_0 = B_1v_1$, and so $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} A_1B_1^{n_r+1} x_0 = A_1B_1v_1$

Again by (4) $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} A_1B_1^{n_r+1} x_0 = u_1$ and therefore, $A_1B_1v_1 = u_1$.

Since A_1 is one to one and by (5), $B_1v_1 = v_1$ so, B_1 has a fixed point. Since B_1 is one to one and B_1 is A_1 - contraction and by the normality we get that B_1 has a unique fixed point. □

Conclusion

Our results are more general than the results of [7].

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